

The Tanzania Development Vision 2050: Empowerment for Teaching Profession and Ethics

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Abstract:

Teachers are among the primary agent of implementing education and training recent reforms together with the Tanzania Development Vision 2050 (*Dira*, 2050) broad goals. The aim of this review focuses on the guiding question that: How should teachers serve the nation ethically in a rapid transforming society, burdened with numerous socio-economic issues, and still make the *Dira* 2050 achievable? The purpose is to bring awareness to education and training stakeholders on the manner of executing duties in the 21st century era. Extensive literature review covers two areas of study. The national visionary matters together with teaching profession and ethics. Literature assisted in understanding the *Dira* 2050 as an empowerment tool for teaching profession and ethics. The Human capital theory and the Deontological theory informed the review. The information was generated by adopting the Wellington's data enquiry framework. Textual analysis method was used to understand the textual examples of ethical values emerged from the *Dira* 2050. Thus, *Dira* 2050 inspires teachers to accommodate new reforms in the sector of education and training, alongside *Dira's* 2050 broad goals, while remaining professional, ethical, and responsible to the nation. A conclusion was made that teachers have great opportunity to make the *Dira* 2050 achievable.

Keywords: *Dira* 2050, Empowerment Ethics, Teaching Profession, Textual Analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A teacher who teaches at any level of education and training in Tanzania has a great opportunity to practice and make the Dira 2050 achievable. This is because the teacher is among the primary agent of the Dira 2050 in transforming the nation into its full inclusive and sustainable development. The teacher ought to recognise and become conscious of the power of a teaching profession and ethics for fulfilling the nation's development visionary plans in the 21st century. Also, the teacher needs to be conscious of extrinsic nation's development forces which influence teacher's intrinsic forces in contributing to national development. This is because the pace of socio-economic development in Tanzania as in other countries is characterised by high skilled man-power, innovative labour force, staff competition, and communication capacities (URT, 2023a). With these characteristics a teacher needs to pose and re-think of what is expected of one-self as a professional teacher, guided by ethical values in the fast moving and competitive world (Komba & Shukia, 2023; Kumar, 2022; Safari, 2024). Here the teacher is expected to remain professional in practicing day to day academic and socio-economic related duties. At the same time the teacher needs to behave in accordance with ethical values in the field of education which is influenced by current development needs (Komba & Shukia, 2023; Kumar, 2022; URT, 2006).

The conceptual links behind this review include the Tanzania Dira 2050, together with Dira's role of empowerment, teaching profession, and ethics. These concepts are to be understood in this review as follows: According to the foreword section of the Tanzania's Dira 2050, an official document Dira 2050 is referred to as a bold, inclusive, and forward-looking transformative roadmap embodies the nation's collective aspirations and sets a clear strategic course for the duration of the next 25 years that is 2050 (URT, 2025a). Further, the concept empowerment refers to the process of transforming, liberating citizens to become conscious of, and inspired to engage in socio-economic development of the nation (Mamatha, 2023). As an empowerment tool, strategically Dira 2050 prioritises investments in various sectors which are agriculture, tourism, the manufacturing, the construction and real estate, mining, the blue economy, the sports and creative industry together with financial and service (URT, 2025a). The investment practices are to be fulfilled by Tanzanian themselves. The practice of integrating Dira's 2050 pillars and drivers into national development plans empowers the present and future generations including teachers to ensure that development outcomes are broad-based and contribute to the realisation of a prosperous, equitable, and high-income nation by 2050 (URT, 2025a).

Regarding teaching profession concept, it is asserted that teaching as a profession engaged in the process of making other professions happen (Halder 2024; Osiesi, Moeng & BIGNAUT, 2025). In the transformation perspective of inclusive and sustainable development, teaching profession transforms and equips individuals with knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes for socio-economic development (Halder, 2024; Komba & Shukia, 2023). Further, the concept; ethics, is referred to as a set of values and principles

which are basic standards guiding individuals to do that which has been agreed upon as the right thing (Sultana, 2014; URT, 2006). Ethical values are universal they guide everybody irrespective of social standing, gender or race. Such ethical values include: integrity, accountability, respect of human dignity, transparency, justice and fairness, stewardship, confidentiality, rule of law, professionalism, honesty, and responsibility to mention some of them (Sultana, 2014; URT, 2025a; URT, 2006). In this review the latter mentioned three ethical values: professionalism, honesty, and responsibility are acknowledged as Tanzania-national core values in the context of public service (URT, 2006). The three core values are very important in guiding the conduct for workers and in particular teachers for this review (URT, 2006). These values provide a moral and professional foundation that enhance teachers' effectiveness, strengthen public trust in the education and training systems and improve the quality of teaching and learning embedded by the core values (Sultana, 2014; URT, 2025a). Dira 2050 positions a teacher not only as a facilitator of knowledge, but also as a role model and an agent of ethical leadership in order to embed ethical core values within teacher professional practices. Teachers' professional ethics is essential for nurturing responsible, skilled, and value-driven learners capable of contributing meaningfully to the goals of Dira 2050.

Despite the timely and strategic structures of understanding and executing the Dira 2050, the in-service teachers and student-teachers experience fundamental changes which are ought to be practiced at various levels of education and training. Although at its earlier stages of implementation, teachers are to use integrated logistics system in performing their duties, be creative in generating power (electricity) for diverse needs, involve in the promotion of Science and Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) trainings, accommodating new curricula, constructing modern libraries and laboratories, shifting to competence-based pedagogical approaches and assessment, accommodating inclusive education needs, engaging in research and development, extending partnership with industries to enhance vocational studies, and the use of digital technologies, as well as participating in career development trainings (URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a; URT, 2023b; UNESCO, 2020).

All these changes are to be acknowledged by teachers as opportunities in the field of education and training. Teachers at any level of education and training are to embrace changes stating from own mindset and still be guided by teaching profession ethical values. The rationale for this article is based on substantiates significance of Dira 2050 as a tool for empowerment. Teachers are empowered in their teaching profession to align their duties with the Dira, 2050. For this reason, the review aims to focus on the guiding main question that: - How should a teacher serve the nation ethically in a rapid transforming society, burdened with numerous socio-economic issues, and still make the Dira 2050 achievable? Understanding of role of a teacher on the Dira 2050 will conscientize and bring awareness to the teacher as the primary agent of transforming the nation to the goals of Dira 2050.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theories used in the review

This review article is guided by theories from the field of human resource, and ethics. The first one is the Human Capital theory of 18th century advocated by Adam Smith (Grugulis, 2024). The theory emphasizes education and training as the foundation of national development. The core argument of this theory asserts that workers accumulate human stocks of knowledge, skills, attitudes, experiences, and values in performing their duties. The human stocks are valuable assets that contribute to their productivity and economic success (Grugulis, 2024). The theory considers education as both a consumer good, providing personal satisfaction, and a capital good, serving as an input for economic and social transformation. In essence, an educated population is considered a more productive population, and investment in education is seen as equally to investment in physical capital such as land or machinery (Deming, 2022; Grugulis, 2024; Rothomi & Rafid, 2023).

Thus, the Human Capital theory seems to encourage teachers to use their education to transform the nation. Also, to teach others to accept changes, and respond to challenges as they create opportunities to transform the nation as strategized by Dira 2050. Regarding teachers be ethical in their profession, the review is also guided by the second theory- the Deontological theory of 1785 propounded by Immanuel Kant (Khasanova, 2024). The theory provides the foundation for professionalism, emphasizing duty, adherence to professional standards, and compliance with codes of ethics. In the context of education and training, the Deontological theory assists educators navigate ethical dilemmas and make decisions that align with their professional obligations and the well-being of their citizens (Khasanova, 2024; Zewdie, 2025). Thus, the principles of professionalism, honest and responsibilities are grounded in the Deontological theory. Generally, the theories used in this review assist in navigating the research question for this study.

2.2 The structure and content of Dira 2050

The official document Dira 2050 is preceded by preliminary pages which are: table of contents, abbreviations and acronyms together with a foreword by the President of the United Republic of Tanzania Her Excellency Dr Samia Suluhu Hassan. The foreword introduces the meaning of Dira 2050 (see section 1.0 of this review), the history of national development since 1961 to 2000s when the Vision 2025 was also launched, its achievements and reasons for the need of the present Dira 2050. The foreword ends by highlighting the essence of Dira 2050 to Tanzanians'. A call was made to all Tanzanians to align their plans with Dira 2050. The last part of the preliminary pages is a preface by Professor Kitila Alexander Mkumbo, the Minister of State President's Office, Planning and Investment. The preface synthesised the need for Dira 2025, the stages and process of its development, and the present Dira's 2050 foundation, pillars and strategic drivers of transformation together with the criteria for identifying priority sectors.

The content of Dira 2050 is described into eight parts namely: Part 1 "Context". This part introduces the United Republic of Tanzania (URT) by explaining its geographical location, population of people, natural resources, cultural diversity within

the country, customs, traditions and heritage like Mount Kilimanjaro, Kiswahili language, National parks and beaches. Also, the countries development journey after independence was traced by acknowledging the work done by the visionary leaders: Mwalimu Julius Kambarage Nyerere, the first president of Tanganyika, and Sheikh Abeid Amani Karume, the first president of the People's Republic of Zanzibar. These leaders strived to bridge ethnic, cultural, and religious divides. The vision of our revolutionary leaders was further strengthened through the adoption of Kiswahili as the national language, fostering a shared identity and reinforcing social cohesion. The history of economic liberation is chronologically traced from the early-independence 1961 to late 1990s. Then after, explanation is given on Vision 2025, its pro and cons and its end time-which is June 2026. This part ends with the forecasted outlook of Tanzania in 2050.

Part 2 is about "The Vision". This part connects the context of Dira 2050 and its' fundamental components. The fundamental components are the key principles that form the basis for realisation of Dira 2050. These are: democracy, rights, and freedoms, dignity, peace and unity, natural wealth and resources, together with culture and national ethos. Also, Dira 2050 set to achieve four key goals. These goals are: a diversified, resilient, inclusive and competitive upper middle-income economy, high quality of life and well-being for all, a nation that conserves and sustainably, efficiently and optimally utilises natural resources, maintains environmental integrity, and its climate change resilient, and a digital empowered society that embraces innovation, drivers the country productivity and competitiveness. Part 2 ends with Dira's 2050 framework which is uncovered in the following next parts. Part 3 is about "The Foundation" of the nation's Dira 2050. The foundation is metaphorically identified as the heart of Dira 2050. The foundation is attributed with practices of good governance and justice, strong and effective local governance, responsible and accountable public service, together with peace, security and stability.

These attributes form the base for Dira 2050 and "glue" or reinforce the pillars, drivers, and transformative sectors essential to the country's transformation into a prosperous, just, inclusive and self-reliance nation. Further, part 4 concerns "The Pillars". The nation's Dira 2050 is supported by the three pillars. The first pillar aims to build a strong, inclusive and competitive economy by creating opportunities for all, the second pillar centres on human capabilities and social development. The third and last pillar is dedicated to environmental integrity and climate change resilience. The pillars address the country core developmental priorities, establishing the necessary framework to achieve the ambitious goals set out in the Dira 2050.

Part 5 is on "The Drivers" to the realisation of the nation's Dira 2050. There are five key drivers which are: integrated logistics, energy, science and technology, research and development also, digital transformation. Integral logistics streamlines supply chains, optimising sources allocation and enhancing efficiency. Science and technology foster innovation, driving advancements that boost productivity and competitiveness. Research and development is essential for creating transformed knowledge and evidence-based solutions that address local challenges and enhance socio-economic growth. Digital transformation facilitates the adoption of disruptive technologies that lead to the

improvement of service delivery through greater efficiency and operational effectiveness. Regarding energy, it drives industrialisation, fosters innovation and improves quality of life by powering economic diversification, unlocking the potential sectors of the economy, raising living standards, and empowering communities. These drivers are crucial for accelerating socio-economic transformation enhancing productivity and improving the quality of life for all citizens, ultimately achieving the goals of the Dira 2050 in Tanzania.

Part 6 “Transformative Sectors”. In order to achieve the nation’s development vision, Tanzania has prioritised key sectors with high potential for economic, social, and environmental transformation for prosperity and sustainable growth. Via agreeable criteria the following are the prioritised sectors. The agriculture sector, tourism sectors, the manufacturing centre, the construction and real estate sectors, mining sector, the blue economy sector, the sports and creative industry, financial sector, and service sector. Part 7 draws the “Implementation Framework” of Dira 2050. Key components for effective execution and lasting impact of the Dira 2050 include strategic prioritisation, phased implementation, strong institutional coordination, and data driven systems to track progress at every stage. The last part is Part 8 on “Forward Looking”. This part summarises Dira’s 2050 journey towards the nation’s development. Dira 2050 extends from the Tanzania Development Vision 2025 to its destination in 2050. Tanzanians with great hope are called to make the Dira 2050 achieve its goals through strategic plans made to its foundation, pillars, drivers and priority sectors.

2.3 Previous related studies

2.3.1 The National Development Vision

In the context of Tanzanian, some scholars have contributed to studies on the national development vision. For example, Mashingia, (2023) had studied on “assessment of the implementation of practical skills in the secondary school curriculum for the realization of vision 2025 in Kilimanjaro region. The study had five research questions focused on (i) status of practical skills subjects, (ii) strategies from implementing practical skills, (iii) perception of teachers on implementation of practical skills, (iv) challenges faced by teachers and students in implementation process, and (v) possible solutions. The research design was mixed approach with convergent design. The sample population was 531. The data were collected through questionnaires, interview guide questions, documents, and observations. The findings include: the need to develop practical skills projects as strategy for implementing practical skills, teachers and students had positive perceptions on involving in practical skills for competence-based learning. Also, interlink between practical skills and employment opportunities. Challenges include inadequate qualified teachers in schools, lack of practical skills pedagogy. Solution to the challenges included Educational Planners to plan refreshers courses for secondary school teachers. The study concluded that Vision 2025 could be realised through students acquiring practical skills for improvising their livelihood. Recommendations made include practical skills subjects such as agriculture and engineering to be introduced to secondary schools (Mashingia, 2023).

Further, in July 2024, a Vision 2050 discussion meeting was held at Tunza Beach in Mwanza Region, Tanzania. In this meeting a paper was presented by Isaac Safari entitled “Towards Development Vision 2050: Better life for every Tanzanian achievable”. The objectives of this presentation was: To provide ideas for Tanzania’s development vision, improve the quality of life for every Tanzanian, encourage national discussion about the future of Tanzania, and suggest policies and priorities for sustainable development (Safari, 2024). The main ideas emanated from the mentioned objectives are: The nation to build a strong and competitive economy, investing in education and skills, promoting good governance, developing infrastructure, strengthening National values and unity, using natural resources wisely, and reducing poverty and inequality (Safari, 2024). Thus, suggestions were given that Tanzania can achieve a better life for its people by 2050 through education, economic growth, good leadership, infrastructure development and responsible use of resources (Safari, 2024).

2.3.2 Teaching profession and ethics

Several scholars have made their contributions to the field of teaching profession and ethics. For example, Osiesi et al. (2025) conducted a study on the professional ethics and teaching for change in the 21st century African schools: The role of teachers’ professional development and curriculum evaluation. The argument behind the study is that if the objectives and the expected standard of the profession are to be attained, especially in the 21st century, concerted efforts need to focus on enhancing and sustaining teachers’ professional ethics which has diverse meanings. The context of the study is on the four main questions: (i) what defines teachers’ professional ethics in Africa? (ii) what changes have the 21st century brought into the teaching profession in Africa? (iii) what is the role of professional development programmes on teachers’ professional ethics and teaching profession in Africa? (iv) What is the role of curriculum evaluation on teachers’ professional ethics and teaching in Africa?

The Moral Development Theory underpinned the study. The study utilised a qualitative systematic literature review methodology. The Enhancing Transparency in Reporting the Synthesis of Qualitative Research-guidelines was used to increase dependability and credibility of the findings. Also, a pluralistic approach called Reflexivity” was employed to integrate and incorporate various and varied point of view. Findings indicate that African law systems, cultural norms, and educational settings define teacher professional ethics in Africa; the 21st century has brought a drastic change to the teaching professional in Africa as it has led to various teaching innovations, new pedagogical demands, changes in the educational structure, and technological improvements; professional development programmes enhance teachers’ ethical awareness, reasoning, and decision-making; while curriculum evaluation impacts teacher development, accountability, instructional methods, professional ethics, and students learning outcomes.

The study concludes that for African schools to be up to date with the demands of the 21st century ethics of the teaching profession and teaching should be pursued and positively transformed through teachers’ professional development and curriculum evaluation. The study suggests that for the future of African education, African teacher

unions and associations revisit and re-evaluate the supposed ethics of the profession, while monitoring teachers on the ethical practice; all levels of the professional development and training programmes for teachers should be funded and organised; and curriculum specialists and developers should consider evaluating the African curricula to update its content in line with what the future portends for the education system in the global space. In relation to the present review, Osiesi et al. (2025) analyses the 21st external forces behind teaching profession and ethical codes. The meanings and practices of key concepts are explained from African context. Also, authors looked at management roles for teachers' professional development and ethical conduct. The roles focus on professional development programmes and evaluation of teaching profession curriculum.

Further, Halder, (2024) carried out a study on the role of professional ethics in teacher education in the light of the National Education Policy (NEP) of 2020 in India. The policy emphasizes on the professional standards of teachers at all levels where professional ethics and values occupy an essential place. The study sought to explore three objectives: (i) importance of professional ethics in teacher education, (ii) the consequences of lack of professional ethics among teachers, and (iii) suggestions and recommendations of NEP 2020 on professional ethics and teacher education. The methodology employed an extensive literature review for data collection. Two of the key national documents used for data collection were the NEP 2020 and a draft of the National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPST). The descriptive analysis method was used to analyse the data. The study found that: the combination of knowledge, skills and competence makes a teacher effective in classroom situation, but the integration of professional ethics can make a teacher an ideal one.

This means that maintaining professional ethics can make a teacher a successful leader and motivator as well as a role model who inspires learners throughout their lives; lack of professional ethics results into the following: teacher's absenteeism, biased attitude towards learners, unfair assessments, lack of teacher-learner positive relationship, and the use of abusive language; suggestions and recommendations by the NEP 2020 state that: all teacher education programmes should emphasize the practice of the Fundamental Duties (Article 51A) of the Indian Constitution along with other Constitutional provisions while teaching any subject or performing any activity; the National Curriculum Framework for Teachers Education (NCFTE, 2022) is drafted to guide all teacher education and trainings.

Thus, the curriculum and pedagogy of the institutions must develop among the learners a deep sense of respect towards the fundamental duties and constitutional values together with a conscious awareness of one's roles and responsibilities in a changing world; the NEP 2020 urged for another common guide that is the NPST should be developed by the NCFTE. The core mission of the NPST is to ensure that all learners at all levels of education are taught by passionate, motivated, highly qualified, professionally trained and well-equipped teachers. The conclusion made for this study is that professional ethics should be an integral part of teacher education programmes. The NEP 2020 assists in understanding how to develop teacher programmes which are more flexible, holistic and integrated to enable learners to be ethical and rational. Similar to the existing study, Halder (2024) uses the NEP 2020 and the NPST as a lance to discuss issues

related to professional ethics for educators who are the source of development. Thus, official guidelines for public service are key to national development.

Furthermore, Peter (2022) undertook a study on managing teachers' codes of ethics and conduct in government secondary schools in Arusha District Council in Tanzania. According to Peter (2022), the quality of education and academic performance of a student depends much on teachers' academic and professional qualifications, and on teachers' compliance with a school code of ethics and conduct. The study objectives were to: (i) sought opinions and experiences on teachers' awareness of codes of ethics and conduct, and (ii) investigated challenges encountered when managing codes of ethics and conduct.

A qualitative research approach and a case study design were opted for the study. The data were collected from 30 participants in 5 out of 36 public secondary schools. Face to face interviews were conducted with 5 heads of school. Questionnaire guides were used to collect the data from 25 teachers. The analysis of the data was done by employing descriptive statistical techniques for numerical data, while the qualitative data were thematically analysed. The findings show that teachers and heads of school were aware of codes of ethics and conduct, but the codes were poorly managed; the major challenges related to poor management of the codes of ethics and conduct were: lack of training for teachers on codes of ethics and conduct, lack of committees for enacting the codes of ethics and conduct, favouritism given to some teachers when their indiscipline cases were reported to the District Education Officer and Teachers Service Department, corruption of cases that involved police investigations, and delays of decisions on indiscipline cases. Recommendations are given that heads of school to increase efforts to ensure proper management of codes of ethics and conduct for teachers. As for the existing review, Peter (2022) shows relationship between teaching profession and ethics, together with their influence on quality education and students' academic performance. This kind of relationship suggests the need for integration between the planned goals for national development and the human power (citizens) who are the implementers of the national development plans.

Nevertheless, Sahin and Yuksel (2021) carried on a study entitled meaning and uniqueness of ethics and ethical teacher behaviours in the teaching profession in Ankara, Turkey. (objectives)The study aimed to determine ethical teacher behaviours according to the opinions of student-teachers and professional teachers. A qualitative research approach and the phenomenological research design were used. 30 participants were involved in the study via interviews. The findings reveal that participants understood the following: the responsibilities of teachers, the respect and importance of the teaching profession, effective teaching, developing health relationships with school members, and benefiting students and society from teachers' professional ethics. Also, the teaching profession should have unique ethical codes for different reasons. Ethical teacher behaviour has emerged within the scope of rights and justice, interest and importance to people and the profession, not to harm or benefit, and the bound of public and private space. The study suggests that professional teaching ethics should be improved in a

manner that the profession can be evaluated in different contexts such as professional, individual and social. Thus, Sahin and Yuksel (2021) clarified that individual teachers are very much aware of ethical conduct. However, they are faced with challenges which call for staff development training programmes. For this reason, this review sees the need to remind teachers of their roles to the national inclusive and sustainable development.

2.3 Literature contribution to this review

Literature by Mashingia (2023) and Safari (2024) which is written in the context of Tanzania development vision, shed light on the visionary content to the present study. Authors forecasted key issues which build the content of the Dira 2050. Regarding teaching profession and ethics, the reviewed literature widens knowledge on the use of related concepts. The importance of official guidelines to the national development was also discussed. These guidelines are to empower citizens to execute the plans made (URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a; URT, 2006). Methodologically, literature reviewed add knowledge on the integration of qualitative and quantitative research approach and different research design such as case study and phenomenological (Mashingia, 2023; Peter, 2022; Sahin & Yuksel, 2021). In addition, extensive literature reviews were conducted, and this showed light on possible sources of information to the current review (Halder 2024; Osiesi et al., 2025). Experiences from different research contexts: Africa, India, Turkey and Tanzania add value to the review with global and local lessons (Halder, 2024; Osiesi et al., 2025; Peter, 2022; Sahin & Yuksel, 2021). Theoretically, only one study used a theory from the field of moral ethics and it has assisted in elaborating concepts used in this review (Osiesi, et al., 2025).

2.4 Lacunae in the reviewed literature

The two studies by Mashingia (2023) and Safari (2024) were published one to two years before the launching event of the Dira 2050. The authors had a lot of suggestions on Dira 2050. The current review described extensively the official Dira 2050 which accommodated most of the ideas suggested previously. Further, most studies focused on one theme from the beginning to the end of the researches for example studies on teaching profession and ethics (Osiesi, et al., 2025; Peter, 2022; Sahin & Yuksel, 2021). The current review is framed by two main themes on the Dira 2050 together with teaching profession and ethics. This enabled the researcher to link education and training matters with socio-economic development of the country. Also, few studies employed theories to their research. This review is informed by theories from the field of human resource (the Human Capital theory) and the field of ethics (the Deontological theory) to navigate the broad theme of this review that is, Dira 2050 as an empowerment tool for teaching profession and ethics. Thus, the present review is very useful to education and training sector because it links the sector with strategies of national development.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research approach and design

A qualitative approach and case study design were employed for deeply understanding of this review article. Through this approach and design Dira 2050 was considered as a tool for empowering teaching profession for ethical public service. This assisted in gaining knowledge on the manner in which Dira 2050 illustrates ways of executing the structured goals of national development into practice. Specific examples of such practices featured in the Dira 2050 were integrated with the ideas behind teaching profession context. Thus, the study main question was systematically inquired (Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Mugenyi & Mokoro, 2022).

3.2 Samples and sampling

In this review article, the researcher employed purposive sampling in selecting a primary document- the Dira 2050 (Mugenyi & Mokoro, 2022). The document provided information on structure and content together with attributes of ethical values for public service. The purposive sampling technique used was instrumental in finding answers to the main question asked on this review (ref. section 1.0 of this article).

3.3 Data collection tools

Document research was used as a tool for data collection. This was important to this study because document research keeps records that trace their history and shed light on current issues (Bowen, 2009; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; MacCulloch, 2012; Mertens, 2015; Nieuwenhuis 2007). The Dira 2050 serves as the main or primary source of data for this study (URT, 2025a). In addition, related scholarly articles, national policies, international policies, and teaching professional publications were also used as secondary sources of information to inform the review (Bowen, 2009; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; MacCulloch, 2012; Mertens, 2015; Nieuwenhuis, 2007).

3.4 Data collection procedures and analysis

The review process adopted the Wellington's (2000) enquiry framework for generating information from documents. The framework involves asking detailed questions on the authorship, context and content, audience, product, intention, presentation, appearance and image as well as style, function and genre (Wellington, 2000). As for the purpose of this article key questions which were asked focused on authorship, context, audience, intention together with the structure and content of the primary document. The answers obtained from these questions assisted in understanding the literal meaning and interpretive meaning of the Dira 2050 (ref. section 1.0, 2.0 & 4.0 of this article).

As for data analysis, textual analysis (discourse type) method was used to examine meanings from the selected texts (Arya, 2020; Fairclough, 1992, 1995). The content of Dira 2050 was categorised according to its available eight Parts of the document. Texts with national ethos vocabulary, phrases, sentences, or paragraphs were identified from four different parts of the Dira 2050 as examples. Steps for textual analysis were applied. These include: close reading of the text several times in order to identify the general ideas,

key words, literary devices, and the tone of the text. This was followed by identifying the central theme of the text and characters involved. Next step was to analyse the language style and literary devices used. Then the context of the text was examined. Finally, the text was interpreted and conclusions made (Fairclough, 1992, 1995; Ponera, 2019). This method of analysis was important to this review article because it allows understanding of most likely interpretations of the Dira 2050 on ethical matters for public servants (Arya, 2020; Fairclough, 1992).

3.5 Research trustworthiness

The trustworthiness of the study was adhered by following criteria proposed by Guba and Lincoln (1989). These include credibility of the available information from the document-Dira 2050 and other literature. This was done by spending long time to re-examine the content of Dira 2050 for contextual and content understanding. Also, the methodology used in conducting the whole study added evidence into the dependability of information from the document(s) and supportive literature. In addition, the confirmability of the findings was ensured by quoting the data drawn from the textual analysis. Interpretations of the findings were supported by theories and discourses which informed the study. Discussion of findings was done based on the themes emerged under the main and specific research question (Bowen, 2009; Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Guba & Lincoln, 1989). Furthermore, the transferability of the findings was addressed by making detailed description of the primary document-Dira 2050. Also, the quotations from the primary and secondary sources of data were used in discussion. This suggested a possibility of allowing findings to be applicable in a similar case of different setting (Creswell & Creswell, 2023; Guba & Lincoln, 1989).

4. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

This section analyses and discusses selected text extracts from Dira 2050. The objective is to identify the manner in which a teacher for example, can serve the nation ethically in a rapid transforming society, burdened with numerous socio-economic issues, and still make the Dira 2050 achievable. The selected texts are found in different parts of the Dira 2050 which are: The foreword, the vision, the foundation, and the last part-forward looking. The section is divided into two main sub-sections: First, the textual examples of ethical values are analysed by looking at the vocabulary used, grammatical features and the tone. Interpretations are made based on the national core values context. Second, discussions are made under the main theme-Dira as an empowerment tool for teachers in implementing education and training reforms to execute the Dira 2050.

4.1 Textual examples of ethical values

4.1.1 The foreword

In the opening words of Dira 2050 the President-Her Excellency Dr Samia explains reasons for the Dira 2050 to exist, its aims, its users, and how to accommodate it in every one's daily deals (ref. sub-section 2.2 of this review). The second sentence of the penultimate paragraph of the foreword reads: "To realise Dira 2050, we must act with determination, foster a culture of execution, and embrace meritocracy and innovation. We must champion accountability and remain steadfast in our commitment to our shared

future”. The text with a visionary tone paints a picture of where the country aims to be by 2050. This text comes closer to the end of the foreword part.

Firstly, the President shows that Dira 2050 ought to be achieved and started by saying “[t]o realise Dira 2050...”. This quotation makes the reader eager to know means to be used to achieve the goals of Dira 2050. Secondly, the President addresses the tasks of achieving the Dira 2050 to all Tanzanians. She said “we” ... The use of first-person inclusive pronoun “we”, signifies unity and collective responsibility that is all citizens of this nation regardless the differences among Tanzanians are to execute Dira’s 2050 goals. After the call has been made, immediately an obligatory tone of power “must”- a modal verb is used by the President to state the manner in which Tanzanians ought to practice and live by the Dira 2050. She said we have to “act with determination, foster a culture of execution, and embrace meritocracy and innovation”. This phrase which is informed by technical and policy-related vocabulary could mean, all Tanzanians are obliged to perform tasks to fulfil the goals which are to be implemented efficiently. These implementers should be rewarded based on ability, performance, and results. Also, new ideas, creative solutions and improvements should be encouraged in implementing Dira 2050 (URT, 2006).

The second sentence continuous... “we must champion accountability”. In the first part of this sentence “champion” has been used as a verb. Meaning to strongly support, defend, or advocate for something, and for this review- Dira 2050 (Oxford Dictionary of English, 2010). A call is made to “we” that could refer to all citizens including the President, to strongly support citizens’ actions and decisions towards Dira 2050. Regarding “accountability”, this is one of the principles of being responsible. Accountability could mean:

- (a) Taking responsibility for actions and decisions (Oxford Dictionary of English, 2010), or
- (b) Recognising that public servant’s primary responsibility is serving the public.
- (c) Treating the public and colleagues courteously especially vulnerable populations like the elderly, sick, children, poor, disabled and other disadvantaged.
- (d) Clarifying of providing direction on promptly and without bias, matters of law, regulations and procedures (URT, 2006 p.22-23).

The last part of the sentence reads; “...remain steadfast in our commitment to our shared future”. This sentence extends and emphasises the call that the citizens and the President not to perplex on reaching the goals and targets of Dira 2050. The inclusive pronoun “our” stands for all Tanzanians, the President representing all those in leadership positions together with the citizens are the owners of the Dira 2050. All together must have a common understanding on how to achieve the broad goals of Dira 2050. Here the President by using visionary tone continues to give reasons for championing accountability in order to achieve Dira 2050 broad and strategic goals. The language used is very formal and standard structured sentence (Fairclough, 1995, 1992).

4.1.2 The vision

In section 2.1 of Dira 2050, there are guiding principles which form the bases for realisation of the Dira 2050. One of the principles is dignity. The Dira 2050 explains “dignity” as a base for making the Dira 2050 achievable. This is practiced by the citizens of Tanzania be respected, valued, and cared for. Also, in the context of part 2 of official document-Dira 2050, dignity requires every individual to enjoy the highest standard of privacy and protection. Together with other guiding principles, “dignity” stands as an umbrella that covers the national ethos. “Dignity” as used in this text means a state or quality of being honour or respect (URT, 2025a; URT, 2006). Dignity as the highest state of valuing people, it fits in qualifying each core value of the nation which are: professionalism, honest and responsibility. Dignity with professionalism is shown through commitment to offer excellent service, being diligent in exercising duties, being impartial when offering service to people, and proper use of official documents. Thus, by doing this dignity will be preserved (URT, 2006). Also, the core value of being honest-upholds dignity by instilling to the citizens the spirit of striving to be truthful, and keep promises while executing duties for public sake (URT, 2006). As for responsibility, dignity is reflected by citizens being loyal and accountable to the ones served, respecting the law and refraining from gender-based misconduct (URT, 2006). Thus, the tone of this text is very formal and policy-driven. The tone reflects the term “dignity” as among the national development principles. Grammatically, only one word “dignity” was nominalised as a way of emphasising the importance of this principle which has very strong and broad meaning in implementation of the Dira 2050.

4.1.3 The foundation

Part 3 of the Dira 2050, sub-section 3.1.3 unpack one of the foundational attributes of Dira 2050. This is about responsible and accountable public service. Public service is considered to be of quality. This is because it influences effective governance, directly shaping policy implementation, service delivery, and management of state affairs (URT, 2025a). As a result, Dira 2050 sees the influence of public service on achieving Dira 2050 goals. The attribute reads that “[i]n recognition of the critical role that public service plays in nation-building, Tanzania has embarked on series of reforms aimed at enhancing efficiency, professionalism and accountability”. Ethical values which could be identified in this text include “efficiency, professionalism, and accountability”. By definition “efficiency” is the state of quality of being efficient (Oxford Dictionary of English, 2010). Also, it is categorised as a principal value of professionalism and responsibility (URT, 2006). “Professionalism is understood as the act of “delivering service of the highest standards” (URT, 2006 p.9). The principal values of professionalism include striving for excellent service, being diligent in exercising duties, being impartial when dealing with people, and proper use of official information (URT, 2006). As for “accountability”, this is a principal value of being responsible. “Accountability” means answering for one’s action and inactions (URT, 2006). The principal values of accountability are already explained (ref. sub-section 4.2.1 of this review).

The next part of the text is the aspiration regarding one being efficient, professional and accountable. The text reads “An efficient, accountable, and transparent public service

that upholds integrity, professionalism, and the rule of law, combats corruption, fosters public trust, and ensures fair and effective use of resources”. Apart from the ethical values which have been defined or explained (efficient, accountable, and professionalism), integrity refers to telling the truth, taking responsibility for one’s action be consistency, and treating people with respect with fairness as well as following rules and moral principles (URT, 2006). In addition, the value of being honest featured in the text as “combats corruption, foster public trust and ensure fair and effective use of resources”. All these bring a closer meaning of an individual to act with integrity (URT, 2006). Further, to be “transparent” means being open in sharing information, being clear in explaining decisions and being honest not misleading people about challenges or mistakes, as well as being willing to allow others to see how and why decisions are made (URT, 2006). In this text, the formal and standard language of attributes and aspirations has been used to motivate citizens, institutions, and stakeholders to achieve the Dira 2050 (Fairclough, 1995, 1992). In addition, technical and ethical related terms were used to explain about the foundation of Dira 2050.

4.1.4 Forward looking

The last paragraph of Part 8 of the Dira 2050 ends the content of the official document-Dira 2050. The third sentence of the paragraph reads “Tanzania will achieve its ambitious goals through a shared purpose, strategic prioritisation and rigorous accountability”. The textual analysis is done to understand the phrase “...rigorous accountability”. Rigorous is an adjective which modifies the noun-“accountability”. The adjective shows strictness of how one is to be responsible. Other terms similar to rigorous which can bring meaning to the identified phrase are precise and thorough (Oxford Dictionary of English, 2010). For this reason, the content of Dira 2050 ends by emphasizing that one must be disciplined enough to execute goals of Dira 2050. The language with a tone of forward looking, projects hope, ambition and strategic directions for the next twenty-five years of the Dira (Fairclough, 1995, 1992). Grammatically, the use of future tense “... will achieve...” shows commitment to execution of the Dira 2050.

4.2 Dira 2050 as empowerment tool for teachers

Teachers are to recognise and be aware of the national Dira 2050 for inclusive and sustainable development. According to Part 8 of the Dira 2050 (URT, 2025a), a call is made that “the vision belongs to everyone... with the right mindset...” Teachers’ mindset should acknowledge the responsibility of being the implementers of the Dira 2050. Through the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology and its institutions, teachers are to be aware of, and accommodate the current system of education and training reforms alongside with Dira’s 2050 broad goals, as well as theoretical principles of the Human Capital and the Deontological theories. The practice of aligning Dira 2050, theories, and education and training reforms needs teachers to abide to the national ethical values of professionalism, honest and responsibility (Halder, 2024; Kumar, 2022; URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a; URT, 2006). Thus, Dira 2050 empowers teachers to interact

and engage with other professions through staff development trainings in order to do the following:

- (a) To understand reasons for establishing an inclusive system of education and training, and how it is practiced in different levels of education and training while Dira 2050 is for inclusive and sustainable development of the nation (UNESCO, 2020; URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a).
- (b) To understand the new system of education and training that is 1+6+4+2/3+3+, and its educational pathways for general and vocational education. The new system and educational pathways seem the foundation of competence-based education (URT, 2023a). Thus, it is very necessary for teachers to understand the narrow and broad meanings of the concept of competence-based education as well as its practical application in different levels of education and training (URT, 2023a; Munisi, 2025; Richard, 2025).
- (c) To involve with competence in the development or review of curricula for various subjects or programmes in different levels of education and training. These curricula could be for general or vocational education. Teachers are to be aware of the priority areas of study which include “Historia ya Tanzania na Maadili” translated into English language as History of Tanzania and Ethics, agriculture, mining, blue economy, tourism, sports, finance, and music. Other areas are: Science, Technology, and Mathematics as well as computer science studies (Mashingia 2023; Sultana, 2014; URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a; URT, 2023c; URT, 2023d). The curricula content of the mentioned areas or subjects should reflect both the disciplinary knowledge and everyday knowledge. This will assist learners in gaining a deeper knowledge (Du Toit, 2011; Osiesi, et al., 2025).

Two reports from UNESCO (2005, 2008) highlight the importance of acquiring deeper knowledge as: it increases learners’ ability both to act as responsible citizen and to add value to society, the economy and political life, it empowers learners to solve complex, high-priority problems encountered in the real world situations of work, society and life, as well as empowers learners to become lifelong inquirers contributing to curriculum that goes beyond mere disciplinary knowledge.

- (d) With competence, to use praxis-oriented pedagogical methods, techniques, strategies and activities in the process of teaching and learning. This involves problem-based learning, self-directed learning, cooperative learning or peer learning, as well as creating space for intercultural curricula through critical dialogue, stories, texts, thinking and rethinking, and participating (Botha, 2011, Le Grange, 2011; Pasha & Pasha, 2012; Sultana, 2014; Wood, 2011). Further, teachers should involve learners to

the task of continuous experimentation, investigation, and inquiry. The participatory teaching and learning could be performed by getting involved in problem-posing and problem-solving activities, team teaching, and critical reflection (Botha, 2011; Du Toit, 2011; Pasha & Pasha, 2012; Osiesi, et al., 2025).

- (e) To become competent in digital literacy in performing various duties in order to align the teaching profession with the national Dira 2050. Such digital systems include: the student registration system, attendance system, communication system, school fees management system, library management system, and employee self service system (URT, 2025a; URT, 2023a). Further, teachers should be aware and being trained on legal and policy framework for example, the Personal Data Protection Act, 2022 which provides legal standards for collecting, processing, storing, and sharing personal information. Also, the Cybercrimes Act, 2015 that addresses crimes committed through computers, mobile phones, and the internet. Nevertheless, teachers should understand and use digital security measures for online interactions as well as managing the use of Artificial Intelligence and ethical values (Osiesi, et al., 2025; URT, 2025a; URT, 2025b; URT, 2022; URT, 2015). This will enable teachers to integrate the 21st century skills in their profession and executing Dira 2050 broad goals.

5. CONCLUSION

In the teaching profession, teachers are the primary agent of transforming the nation into its inclusive and sustainable development. Teachers have a great opportunity to work with many stakeholders including: learners, parents/guardians, employers, colleagues, community, and industries as well as other service sectors. Thus, teachers could communicate, collaborate and bring awareness to other professions on the need to implement the Dira 2050. For this reason, teachers should act professionally, honestly, and be responsible in fulfilling their duties while striving to accommodate valuable education and training reforms in the process of executing the Dira 2050.

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